

glossy black, with yellow basal antennal segments, yellow-brown apices of femora, tibiae, and tarsi (see figure). The pronota are smoothly punctated and

each elytron has 10 longitudinal rows of minute pits. The tibiae of the third pair of legs possess a small apophysis along

the mid-dorsum, dorsolateral combs of hairs near the apical half, and a tooth at the apices. ♂

Granulosis of the rice brown semilooper *Mocis frugalis*

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Rice brown semilooper *M. frugalis* (Fab.) (Lep: Noctuidae) is one of a complex of tropical lepidopterous rice pests. It occurs in flooded rice, but is more abundant in upland rice.

M. frugalis populations seldom occur in damaging levels because they are inhibited by natural parasites, predators, and diseases.

We collected last-instar *M. frugalis* larvae that were infected with a virus disease from a lowland field near Roxas, Palawan, Philippines. Diseased larvae were lemon yellow with swollen abdominal segments (Fig. 1). At later disease stages, the larvae turned dark and milky-white fluid oozed through the integument. Examination of the fluid with a phase contrast microscope showed refractive granules with Brownian movement.

Diseased larvae were macerated in distilled water with a glass homogenizer for further identification and purification. The suspension was filtered through cotton wool and centrifuged for 30 min to remove the bacteria. The precipitate was washed three times with distilled water to obtain a crude extract.

1. Larva of *Mocis frugalis* (Fab.) infected with granulosis virus.

2. Electron micrograph of capsules of *Mocis frugalis* stained with 2% phosphotungstic acid (X 27,600). a =an aberrant, sickleform capsule.

3. Virion released from the capsule after 2 h treatment with 0.05 M NaCO_3 + 0.17 M NaCl at room temperature. (X 22,380). c = empty capsule, rv = released virion, v = virion in the capsule.

The extract was layered on a 20–70% (V/V) glycerol gradient, then centrifuged at 10,000 rev/min for 15 min in a Beckman SW 27 rotor. The virus was collected at the 35–40% glycerol band. These bands were centrifuged at 12,000 rev/min for 20 min using a Beckman Mod. L5-65 and the resulting pellet was resuspended in a small amount of water.

The virus suspension was layered on 30–65% (W/W) linear sucrose density

gradient then centrifuged at 25,000 rev/min for 90 min. The band was collected at 55% sucrose band and centrifuged again at 20,000 rev/min for 30 min. The pellet was collected, diluted with water, and the process was repeated.

After centrifugation, the purified virus capsules were resuspended in water and centrifuged at 12,000 rev/min for 20 min to form a precipitate. A small amount of the virus capsule suspension was stained in a grid for 1 min with 2% phosphotungstic acid (PTA) for electron microscope examination.

The capsules were ellipsoidal, but an aberrant sickle-form also was observed (Fig. 2). Capsules were 433 nm long and 243 nm wide. Each capsule contained a single virion (nucleocapsid). A single rod-shaped virion typical of granulosis was embedded in a capsule (Fig. 3). They averaged 301 nm long and 83 nm wide. The virions were negatively stained with 2% PTA.

Virions in the capsules were obtained after treatment on the slide with equal volume of 0.05 M NaCO_3 + 0.17 M NaCl at room temperature. The protein capsule dissolved after 2 h of gentle stirring, but the virions were released after more than 3 h.

The disease was identified as granulosis. This is the first report of it attacking *M. frugalis*. ♂

Effect of neem product foliar sprays on rice pests

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We studied the effect of foliar spraying of three neem products on the incidence of rice pests in two field experiments at PES in Tirur. The 1984–85 trials comprised five treatments replicated four times and laid out in a simple